

THE MONAD IN POTENTIA

Caio César Costa Santos¹

Abstract: The concept of “monad” is vast and broad. In this essay, the Leibnizian concept of “monad” ([1714] (2016)) will be presented. For Leibniz, the monad is a part as well as the entire universe. However, here, a single point of your *Monadology*, namely, the monad *in potentia* (in power). That is, how do these simple substances form *transform* in composites?. Our method is phenomenological. And the objective is to clarify a little more about the *process* of these substances.

Keywords: Monad. Power. Substance. Part. Universe.

Introduction

Leibniz ([1714] (2016)), in his *Monadology*, observed that, in the metaphysical situation of the immensity of the universe, *coexistence* a type of *substance* (properly “celestial” and/or “divine”) that *would form* all things in this universe precisely in their character of *uniqueness*, *uniqueness* and/or *equality* between substances - this *substance* would be the “monad” or “simple substance”. Perhaps, in this Leibnizian configuration, such “monads” would be “unique” because they would come from the “Unique”. Still, for Leibniz, God (or *the architect* or *the author* as he calls it) would have chosen the most perfect of forms in the creation of *shape* of the universe and the most perfect content in the creation of *interiority* of the universe. Follow the words of Leibniz himself ([1714 (1977)) - “From the supreme perfection of God it follows that, in producing the universe, He will have chosen *the best possible plan*, where there is the greatest variety *with the best land order; of place and time; with maximum effect produced* through the simplest processes; *with maximum power, knowledge, happiness and goodness in creatures*, that the universe could welcome. As all possibilities in God's understanding aspire to existence in proportion to their perfections, the result of all these aspirations will be the current world *as perfect as possible*. And, without that, it would not be possible to give a reason why things were *like this*; and not otherwise” (LEIBNIZ, [1714] 1977, p. 9, emphasis added). The surprising thing to realize is how much Leibniz presents us with a simple, current, but profound and absolutely synthetic vision of how God possibly had *created* all things in His absolute perfection. Do you realize that God, in his absolute extraordinariness, has

¹ Phenomenological psychoanalyst. Degree in Linguistics, Philosophy and Religious Sciences. Master in Linguistic Studies.

freely provided us with the composition, for example, of a simple and unique creature, such as a human-animal and, in this composition, *unique*, has known how to execute, in a total and absolute way, the very composition of this simple creature, being, at best, *as perfect as possible*. Within this, it is clear, in addition, that, as a creature, we can, truly like God, even arrive in our own way and close to the supreme intelligence, dissecting, within the divine acts themselves, donated by divinity to the simplicity of the creature (the simple intellect) the composition of the universe and ourselves.

God, then, happens, not just as the *author* this sometimes indecipherable *work*, but also as our *viewer* or, in Leibniz's words, our *monarch*. That said, perhaps this is why Spinoza ([1677] (2009)) said that “the infinite mind of the creature is part of the infinite mind of God”. And, in the meantime, if *candle a power your potentiality* of the noble, sovereign and human act of being a creature, having God as the *agent* or *author* or even ours *monarch* or *judge*. In this sense, the *organon* of life would be produced with the most perfect perfection possible when God, in His goodness and supreme intelligence, gave birth and produced that which Leibniz discovered, with absolute certainty, in the true existence of *monads* or *simple substances*. So, in this essay, I intend to discuss some words not concerning these substances in a total way (that is, the infinity of their acts and characters), but a single point, in this case, essential in monads - their character of *mirroring and/or reflection* or, in a word, your *virtuality* and yet, the way as such substances *relate* and *are produced* being themselves just a *mirror (speculum)*. With this, we will see why the author of this essay titled it “The monad *in power*”.

The way to treat monads like a mirror

In *Principles of Nature and Grace founded on Reason*, Leibniz ([1714] (1977)) says categorically - “nature is full of life”. And, in our understanding, “it is full of life” simply because of the “monads”. This is true because one thing, *be full of life*, is, at the same time, *full of itself* because what we are in our depths *reflects* actively in who we are in life. Thus, “life” here is synonymous with “fullness” or “totality”. In other words, the fullness of life reverberates in the life of each creature which, according to Leibniz, is associated in a perfect and inseparable way, with the synthesis of simple substances that, in their own way, are *composite* or a *composed of substances*. It turns out that, according to him, such “substances” are both around the entire contour of the fullness of life, and within *of each element of life*. For Leibniz, “life” means “substance”, so, to the extent and in the perfect order possible, the “substance of life” is a perfectly ordered set of *monads*. Therefore, it would be in the *simplicity* of a simple substance that would be found at *multiplicity* of its parts and elements and, thus, the production of *new* substances, as he himself

says, “because, the *simplicity* of the substance does not prevent *multiplicity* of the modifications that must be found together in this same simple substance” (LEIBNIZ, 1977, p. 3, emphasis added).

Leibniz ([1714] (1977, p.4, emphasis mine) says about monads - “and the principle of their *uniqueness is surrounded* of a *mass* formed by an infinity of other monads, which constitute the proper body of this central monad and according to the affections *from him* represents her, as in a kind of *center*, the things that are external to it”. For us, this is the main characteristic of Leibnizian monads, their *self-production in reflection (and/or reaction) mode* in the sense that each one of them is unique and does not have a direct relationship with the others, therefore, if they are “unique” they are also “unequal”, but, like atoms, they do not meet and mismatch with the strength of their energy of opposite frequency, but, on the contrary, it is properly the character of *uniqueness* which makes them, in reality, *one like the others*. Like this, *the equality of simple substances* it would not only be the union of its most essential parts, but such “equality” between them is precisely in its compositional synthesis. In other words, the very compound of monads is the result of the synthesis of their composition. It is as if we could say: “a *monad or simple substance* It is everywhere as it is nowhere.” Such substances are “unique” and, therefore, “unequal”, but, as Leibniz himself says, there would therefore be a *mass* which is surrounded between the monads that makes this first set of simple monads a reality *composite*. Leibniz, in his *monadology*, emphasizes that a set of monads is actually reflected in its synthesis, but each of these “syntheses” are *composite* by the *intervals* that intersect between simple substances. Let's now imagine when the spider begins to weave its threads without, however, ceasing to be entangled by them. The same is - *a set of monads*. Here, that “mass” that Leibniz defined as what makes such substances meet, is here metaphorized by the threads woven by the spider. Furthermore, such wires have a *viscosity* which causes the possible prey to be contained in that “skein”. The same is a set of simple substances; in the example of the spider, the prey is unable to “see” such threads and ends up getting tangled up, while, in monads, we neither see it nor perceive it, but, in fact, *they exist*. Thus, in every part of the universe, each of these parts, we “see” in that “part” a set of monads that, on the perceptual view, appear to be the same, but, deep down, are *heteroclitites, unique*.

In this sense, since the monads are correlating in the interior background of an internal activity when its internal part is other monads, Leibniz sees in this the characteristic of the reality of the *mirroring*. Let's see: “And, as by virtue of the plenitude of the world, everything is connected and each body acts on any body, more or less depending on the distance, *and is affected by it by reaction*, it follows that each monad is a *living mirror*, or *endowed with internal activity, representing the universe from your point of view*, and it is as ordered as the universe itself” (LEIBNIZ, 1977, p.4, emphasis added). In this, we see, by nature, how monads themselves produce others and thus *successively* (as well as *retroactively*). A curious note: Leibniz discovered the

existence of monads just as, for example, Einstein also discovered the relativity between bodies in the sense *space-time* or like Copernicus who discovered that it was the Sun that revolved around the other planets. Leibniz then discovered “monads”; a kind of divine substance that *co-create* everything, therefore, if the universe is purely a “reflection”, all monads are *he*. So, the sense that “each monad mirrors the other” is naturally found in the character of “affection” and “reaction”, that is, each of these substances, in their *uniqueness*, carries, within itself, the reflection of the other when affected by the reaction of the same. In the previous substance the current substance appears and from the current substance the previous reflection of this same current substance. We can say like this, all *rest* or *accumulation* or *trail* of the antecedent substance *represents in a naturally reflexive way* the potency value of the subsequent substance. In this case, it would be “act” and “potency”.

With this sense, the monad reacts within its own body, composed in it of the rest of the previous reaction of the antecedent monad. Thus, one could say again that a set of monads are found in the *intervals*. And, such “intervals” would be like that *mass* that make them equal even though they are “unique” by nature. For example, in the movement of bodies, the monads are there, weaving, above all, the perfect harmony of movement between them. Therefore, I emphasize once again, they are their own “intervals”. They are like that because they are - *the very interval between things*. When a body moves, it leaves the rest of its movement in space; Both this “rest” and the movement that is now actual are part of the dynamic and colorful activity of the monads. This not only in bodies, but also in souls and/or spirits. The proportion with which monads build things in the universe *represents* perfectly the “architectonics of life”, both in *content* or *substrate* of her, as in her infinite *depths*. We can say like this: “the monad as a simple substance is both in the deep and in the simple”. In other words, wherever “life” is, naturally and perfectly, that substance will be *leaf*. It would be, in this sense, both the depth and the simplicity of the “architectonics of life”. Both the formal parts of the universe and its informal parts. So, as an example, the formal is formal because it was an informal because from this “informal” a formal was produced and from the reaction of this “formal” the next one was produced and *like this ad infinitum*.

As in the previous quote, as shown by Leibniz, the monads begin to act in everything, as well as in the “humours of the eyes when the rays of light are concentrated with greater strength”. In other words, according to him, both the “relief” of the ocular image and its “distinction” are effects of the *composed* of monads, in this case, “eyes”. Still in this example, according to Leibniz, the monads are capable of this because they have “organs adjusted” and perfectly “sensitive” to the point that, within themselves, in the case of the humors of the eyes, they receive all the impressions in their own body. Still, for Leibniz, every monad is, at most, a *perception* and, in the case of the eyes, with their power of impression, it *participate* perfectly and completely the functioning of this

“sophisticated organ”, from the *eco* (as he himself states) of the impressions that a set of monads receives from the composition of a visual image in the architecture of the eye. Just like an “iron plate” *print* on the animal a “mark”; in the case of vision, with perception accompanied by memory, the monad can *print* and *bind*, together with the light rays from the atmosphere, the image corpuscle reflected by the eyes. In this way, monads, in general, are part of a single, organized, ordered and systematized principle, whose ultimate purpose is *the life of all substance*.

The monad *in potentia* (*in power*)

We return again to Leibniz's illustrious presentation (1977, p. 6, emphasis mine) when he says - “modern investigations have taught us, and reason confirms, that living beings, whose organs are known to us, that is, plants and animals are not born from putrefaction or chaos, as the ancients thought, but *of preformed seeds* and therefore *the transformation of pre-existing living beings*”. In the introduction to this essay, we say along with Leibniz, “in nature everything is full and connected”, which now means that the entire formation of a given thing was the *protoformation* or *the rest* of previous training. In this sense, observation of this point makes us believe that things did not appear out of nothing or from a nothing (or state of chaos), on the contrary, as Leibniz himself states, all these things have a *source* or a *origin* and this is *God*. Leibniz even, in his writings, calls “God” “Substance” or even the “Primary Substance” because now if there is *order*, *shape* and *perfection* in the universe, all of this today that we know of in part can only have been the result of a simple act and this act, here, in the Leibnizian sense, was “God”. For, as in the Thomist tradition, “God is the pure act” or “the first cause of all things”. So, He is the *author* and *monarch*, at the same time, that is, *creates* and *king*. (Leibniz). Modern physics has only now authentically concluded that “nothing in the universe can be created or destroyed, because everything is energy, therefore, everything can only be *transformed* (or “renewed”). At this point, we are in agreement that a simple seed that appears in the universe was *result*, without a shadow of a doubt, the *rest* from those other previous seeds or even from another type of compound such as the remains of fruits, leaves or even certain animals. (*metempsychotic*). This was confirmed by Leibniz himself (1977, p. 7, emphasis mine) when he says - “And what was just said about large animals also happens in the generation and death of spermatic animals themselves; to mean, *are the increments* of other smaller sperm, in proportion to which they can pass for large, *since in nature everything tends towards infinity*”.

Within this context, the Oxford dictionary says something similar when defining the word “metempsychosis” - “cyclical movement whereby the same spirit, after the death of the former body

in which it inhabited, *returns* to material existence, *cheering* successively the physical structure of plants, animals or human beings". In order to attest to this thought, Leibniz's philosophy is much closer to a "metamorphosis" than a "metempsychosis" as Leibniz himself says - in the universe, "there is not a metempsychosis, but a metamorphosis". In other words, even if it is a reality *transmigration between material bodies* (universal law), yet the *law of evolution* it is more about the "transformation" and/or "renewal" of things than their state of "decomposition". So, as an example, the *rest* of a dead living being will be perfectly "absorbed" by the substance of the earth which, from an organic perspective, will distribute and start to function, at the same time, as *nutritious* for everything around, as well as for *other substances* that, says *feedback* of these "substances", the *rest of the nutrient* not known to her, it will be perfectly *taken advantage of by another* and so on and/or retroactively. Thus, the "composition of things in life" is, in truth, that is, in its foundation, a "decomposition of themselves". Everything else or "dead" tissue *It's as if you were "alive" to another substance* Therefore, everything in the universe is interconnected. Because, once again with Leibniz (1977, p. 8) - "the present movement that exists in matter derives from the previous one and this also from another previous one".

In metempsychosis, for example, the rest of the preceding matter is the driving movement for the emergence of subsequent matter and this is the previous movement of itself. In our view, with regard to monads in a state of transformation like this, that is, from the putrefaction of dead matter to the formation of another and new type of substance, the monads participate perfectly in both one state and the other. Because, at the same time that the body is removing its "dead part", there is, let's say, a certain amount of "aliveness" in this because the dead tissue becomes "alive" when being *pierced* to another substance. The monad *in power* here it would be precisely this "mirroring the mirror within the mirror itself"; it is as if it were the properly executed representation of the mirror's reflective crystals within itself; *the mirror in and/or in front of the mirror*. The monad is the "mirror" as well as its "reflection". Like this, *each monad is the mirror of another; as well as the reflection of another*. Therefore, in the proper body of the "monads", their formation and transformation would not be a metempsychosis, but a "metamorphosis" because the proper body of one monad is the proper body of another. Thus, according to Leibniz, the monad is properly and perfectly a "living mirror" and not an "artificial or dead mirror". Monads are and always are *lives*, like everything in life, is also *vivo*, even a dead part, because, in the "dead", other "substances" are composed that make it "alive".

Therefore, in the "metamorphosis of monads", the formation of a *he was* the transformation of the previous monad. Thus, the course or current of life does not necessarily pass successively, although continuously, but it is "successive" because it is "retroactive", as is the relationship of the past with the present and the future. In the case of the present, the past is both the act and the

potency of the present or the past appears as in a dead or alive state; everything will depend, in the case of humans, on which “place” their “mode-temporal consciousness” is located. In one or the other, in the case of time and monads; they will always be *participating* of this process, whether in *flash* of the feeling of a memory, whether in *vivacity* of the brilliance of the current presence. I think that, according to Leibniz, the perfection of the universe (its contour, as well as its inherent vivacity) depends, to a large extent, on *of the perfection of the architecture of the monads* when the universe, since it emerged (and/or appeared) is a living witness to the presence of these “substances” so *unique* and *essential*.

With a composition of human and organic nature, God, in His infinite goodness and power, enabled us to be what we are by being the *true* of its great mysteries. God, observed and has observed, His perfect organization of the One Life and, in this primordial uniqueness, awakened, from its simplest substances (the monads), the architecture of life! See that each substance such as the body, soul and spirit are contained *in perfect compositional harmony*, where, in natural reason, it will be impossible to perceive such simplicity in its perfection. Let us see Christ, authentic son of God, how much his *composition* while a “living and human being” was *as perfect as possible*, reflecting the grand simplicity of its composition in its perfect earthly existence. So what God said should be done, Christ *he did*. Therefore, like Christ, we are also “children of God” and “humans” like Christ. We're just not *the living uniqueness of Christ* because he is and was a *monad*, and we, as children merely *mortals* and *terrestrial*, we are *other*. For Leibniz, by the simple fact that we are creatures of God's creation, His perfection is reflected *in our entire being* when, as living beings, *we resemble* with the power, love and goodness of God the Father, he says - “concerning the rational soul or spirit, there is something more than in monads or simple souls. He is not only a mirror of the universe of creatures, but also *an image of divinity*. The spirit not only has a perception of the works of God, but is also capable of producing something that resembles them, albeit in a small way... and, upon discovering the sciences according to which God ordered things, it *imitate* in his department and in his small world, where he is allowed to act, what God does in the big one” (LEIBNIZ, 1977, p. 11).

In this view, it would simply be like this - “as living and organic beings, having body, soul and spirit, we are a small monad. Every thing in the universe is a small monad, being God or the One, the simple substance or large monad. In other words, everything is small and only God is big because we see things through a small prism or point and this will never be big. God sees great from the beginning, *before and after the start*, from the beginning. We are a small point when God is our big point and nothing else, nothing else is big, precisely because we need an architect, as well as a monarch and we already have this - *God*. And therefore, “how *true pure love* consists of the state that leads to finding enjoyment and pleasure in the perfections and happiness of what one loves,

such love will give us the greatest pleasure of which one can be capable, when God is its object” (LEIBNIZ, 1977, p .12).

Conclusion

“Nature is full”; “everything in the universe is connected”; “everything in the universe is transformed”. With this short essay, we can understand one of the infinite *shapes* of God's greatness in creating, *in the range of created things*, a simple substance created called a “monad”. As at the beginning of the introduction we say - “the monad is in *shape*, as well as in the *content*”; What does it mean to tell us that *all* what is a *composed* the monads *represent*. In this sense, Creation was made. And there is nothing to change or alter. Since monads are purely “the composition” of everything, it remains to say that God could not choose *the most perfect raw material possible* than - *the monads*. Despite being alive and similar to God, no one is able to “see” such substances when God, in His entirety and in His perfection, *represents* the most perfect juice of all substances, *simple* and *composite*. Thus, the monad *in power* it would be nothing more than the representation of the simple in the compound and the compound in the simple, at all points and in all atmospheres.

REFERENCES

- LEIBNIZ, G. *Princípios da natureza e da graça fundados na razão*. Portugal: Colibri, 1977.
_____. *Monadologia*. Portugal: Colibri, 2016.
SPINOZA, B. *Ética*. São Paulo: Autêntica, 2009.